

STUDIES ON SOME ENGINEERING PROPERTIES OF *ACHA* (*DIGITARIA EXILIS*) STARCH

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14020887

ABSTRACT

This study investigated some engineering properties of *acha* starch with the view of promoting its usage in food processing. Starch was extracted from *acha* grain following a documented procedure with little modification and a portion was modified. The physicochemical, rheology and thermal properties were investigated following standard procedures. The moisture contents ranged from 2.85 to 10.64%. Loose and packed bulk densities, the least gelation concentration, density ratio and porosity ranged between 0.32 to 0.51 g/ml, 0.39 to 0.66 g/ml, 8 to 16% (w/v), 75.21 to 82.19%, and 17.80 to 24.78%, respectively. Similarly, the Carr index had a range of 21.28 to 33.00% and Hausner ratio ranged from 1.22 to 1.33, indicating the starch samples had a fair (native starch), very poor (modified starch) and good (potato starch) flow properties, using Carr standard. The amylose, amylopectin and amylose-amylopectin ratio contents obtained range from 24.07 to 29.77%, 70.23 to 75.93% and 0.32 to 0.42%, respectively. Also, the thermal properties of the samples measured using Differential Scanning Calorimeter (DSC) ranged between 72.7 to 83.6 °C, 87.38 to 106.4 °C, 89.6 to 106.2 °C and 6.27 to 33.5 °C for onset temperature, peak temperature, end temperature and temperature range, respectively. The viscosity values obtained ranged from 408.65 – 665.2 and 417.9 – 447.1 mPa.s for native and modified *acha* starch, respectively. Hence, this study provides engineering data in relation to process design, control and bulk handling with a view to extending the usage of *acha* starch samples in the food processing industry.

Keywords: *Acha*, Starch, Physicochemical, Rheology, Thermal properties

INTRODUCTION

Starch is a naturally occurring biodegradable polysaccharide molecules obtained from various plant sources (Abbas *et al.*, 2010). The major sources of starch are cereals (rice, wheat, sorghum, millet, barley and maize), roots and tubers (yam, potatoes and cassava) and other plant sources such as banana, plantain, breadfruit, sago and arrow root (Tagliapietra *et al.*, 2021). The contribution of Starch to the textural properties of some foods makes it an important agent of thickening, stabilizing, gelling, bulking and water retention (Singh *et al.*, 2007). It has also found application in non-food industries such as textiles; pulp and paper; chemicals and pharmaceuticals; biofuel production; and mining and building (Przetaczek-Roznowska, 2017).

The world's production of starch ranged from 88.1 and 97.7 mt in 2020 with maize, cassava, wheat and potatoes contributing 75, 15, 7 and 4%, respectively (Olivier and Jose, 2023). The demand for starch is expected to increase geometrically among food and non-food processing industries (Kumar *et al.*, 2023). This increasing demand for starch has justified sourcing for starch from other readily available non-conventional starch sources such as *acha* (*Digitaria exilis*). *Acha*, an underutilized cereal crop mostly grown in West Africa belongs to the family of *graminaea*. The major producers of the cereal crop in West Africa are

Nigeria, Guinea, Burkina Faso and Mali (Arueya and Oyewale, 2015). In Nigeria, its cultivation is mainly in the Northern region with Plateau State being the largest producer of the crop with an average of production of 20 mt annually (Cruz, 2004). *Acha* performs excellently in low-moisture and low-fertility soils that may not support other cereal crops. They are known to mature within a short period of 6 – 8 weeks and have high starch content (Arueya and Oyewale, 2015). *Acha* has good content of sulphur amino acids which are important for the proper functioning of the heart and nerve transmission (Jideani and Jideani, 2011). Due to the ease of digestion of *acha*, it has been traditionally recommended for children, people manifesting intolerance to gluten (celiac diseases), sick people, diabetic patients and patients with stomach diseases (Cruz, 2004). In spite of the nutritional and economic importance of *acha*, its use in the production of value-added products is very low. In addition there is dearth of information regarding mechanization of its production, processing, handling, storage, and distribution (Philip and Isaac, 2012). Therefore, this work focuses on some engineering properties of the starch from *acha*, with the view of providing engineering data that will enhance its processing, handling, and utilization in food formulation and development.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Source of Materials

Acha (*Digitaria exilis*) grains devoid of defects was purchased from central market, Ilorin, Kwara State, Nigeria while all chemicals needed for this work will be of analytical grades.

Sample Preparation

Five kilograms of Acha grains were washed and destoned with portable water. The cleaned acha grains were steeped in water for 24 h at 28 °C. Thereafter, the steep solution was discarded and the grains were re-washed with potable water. The steeped acha grains were wet-milled using a laboratory milling machine (Falling Number 3100, Huddinge, Sweden). The slurry obtained was diluted with 5 L of distilled water and subsequently screened using a muslin cloth. The filtrate was subsequently allowed to settle for 3 h in a stainless-steel decanting bowl, after which the supernatant was discarded (Emeje *et al.*, 2012). The starch slurry was then air dried. The starch flakes obtained were milled in a laboratory milling machine (Retsch GM300, Germany) and sieved (sieve size: 500 µm) to obtain starch flour. The native starch yield was expressed in percentage dry weight of native starch per weight of cleaned sample. The native starch obtained was then divided into two portions. The first lot was stored in properly labelled zip-lock bags while the second lot was modified using acid.

Acid modification of breadfruit starch: A portion of the native starch sample was modified using a procedure documented by Adebayo *et al.* (2021). About 200 g of the native starch was suspended in 400 ml of 6% (w/v) HCl solution at 27 ± 2 °C for 1 h without stirring. After hydrolysis, the suspension was neutralized with 10% (w/v) sodium hydroxide solution to terminate the reaction. The starch slurry was then washed with distilled water, air-dried and milled (Retsch GM300, Germany). The modified starch was sieved using a 500 µm mesh sieve and the starch flour obtained was stored in a properly labelled Ziploc bag till its usage.

Acha Starch Yield

Starch yield was determined using equation 1:

$$SY = \frac{W_S}{W_E} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

Where: SY = starch yield, %; W_S = weight of starch flour, g; W_E = Weight of edible portion, g.

Determination of Physicochemical Properties of Acha Starch Flour

Physicochemical properties such as bulk density, amylose and amylopectin ratio, flow property and least gelation concentration were determined using standard procedures.

Moisture content: The moisture content determination was carried out using AOAC (2005) Official Method 925.10. The moisture content was determined using equation 2:

$$M. C_{db} = \frac{W_1 - W_2}{W_2} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

Where: W_1 = weight of the starch powder before drying, g; W_2 = weight of the starch powder after drying, g, $M. C_{db}$ = moisture content on dry basis, %.

Packed bulk density: Packed bulk density was determined according to the method documented by Adebayo *et al.* (2021). A 10 ml graduated cylinder was filled with a known weight of the sample, and bottom of the cylinder was gently tapped several times on a laboratory work bench until there was no further diminution of the sample level after filling to the 10ml mark of the cylinder. Packed bulk density was then calculated using equation 3:

$$BD = \frac{W_s}{V_s} \quad (3)$$

Where: BD = bulk density, g/ml, W_s = weight of starch sample, g, V_s = volume of sample, ml.

Loose bulk density: Loose bulk density was determined using a method documented Adebayo *et al.* (2021). A 10 ml graduated cylinder was gently filled with starch sample. The volume occupied was recorded. Loose bulk density was then calculated using equation 3.

Density ratio and porosity: The density ratio (Dr) which is the ratio of the bulk density to true density expressed as a percentage was determined using equation 4. While porosity was determined using equation 5:

$$D_r = \frac{\rho_B}{\rho_T} \times 100 \quad (4)$$

$$P = \left(1 - \frac{\rho_B}{\rho_T}\right) \times 100 \quad (5)$$

Where: Dr = density ratio, ρ_B = packed bulk density, g/ml, ρ_T = loose bulk density, g/ml, P = porosity.

Flowability properties: The flowability of the sample was determined using the data obtained from packed bulk density and loose bulk density of the starch to evaluate the sample's compression and compaction. The Hausner ratio and Carr index values were evaluated to ascertain the flow property of the sample. The Hausner ratio was then calculated as a ratio of the packed density of the starch to its loose bulk density as shown in equation 6 (Adebayo *et al.*, 2021) while the Carr index as the ratio of the difference between the packed density and loose density of the sample to its loose density. This is expressed as a percentage as shown in equation 7 (Adebayo *et al.*, 2021). The Hausner ratio values were then compared with the Carr index values to ascertain if the flow was excellent, good, fair, or poor.

$$H_R = \frac{\rho_{\infty}}{\rho_0} \quad (6)$$

$$C. I = \frac{\rho_B - \rho_T}{\rho_T} \times 100 \quad (7)$$

Where: H_R = Hausner ratio, ρ_{∞} = asymptotic constant density after certain number of taps, ρ_0 = initial bulk density,

C.I = Carr index, ρ_B = Packed bulk density, g/ml, ρ_T = Loose bulk density, g/mL

Gelation and least gelation concentration: A method documented by Adebayo *et al.* (2021) was used in the determination of gelation concentration of the samples. A known amount of starch sample was dispensed in distilled water to make 5 ml total volume and starch concentration of 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 14, 16, 18 and 20% (w/v) in test tubes. The mixture was then stirred to ensure a homogenous mixture was formed. This was then placed in a laboratory mixing machine at high speed for 2 min. after which centrifugation was carried out for 15 min. to eliminate any air present, in form of bubbles, in the sample. The samples were evaluated for gel formation by the least concentration end point method. For determination of least gelation concentration, test tubes which contained the samples were heated in a boiling water bath for 1 h followed by rapid cooling under running cold tap water. The test tubes were cooled further in a refrigerator at a temperature of 4 °C for 2 h. The strength of the coagulum was evaluated by inverting the test tube. The least gelation concentration was determined when the sample in the test tube did not fall out or slip.

Amylose and Amylopectin Ratio Determination

The Amylose content was determined using a method documented by Adebayo *et al.* (2021). A sample of 100 mg was measured into a 100 ml standard flask, and 1.0 ml of ethanol (95%) and 9.0 ml of 1.0 M NaOH were then added. The mixture was then heated in a boiling water-bath for 10 min to gelatinize the starch. The gelatinized starch solution of 5.0 ml was subsequently transferred to a 100 ml standard flask, and 1.0 ml of 1.0 M acetic acid and 2.0 ml of stock iodine solution were thereafter added to it. The volume was further made up with distilled water. The content was thoroughly vortexed and allowed to settle for 20 min. The resultant color was allowed to develop and the absorbance was read at 620 nm using a UV-Spectrophotometer (*Jingxue Scientific Instrument Co. Ltd, Shanghai; Model – 752S*). The amylose content was then calculated from the standard curve of potato amylose. The amylopectin content was calculated by subtracting the determined amylose content from 100 and expressing it in percentage (%) as shown in equation 8:

$$AC = 100 - ac \tag{8}$$

Where: AC = Amylopectin content, ac = Amylose content, %

Determination of Engineering Properties

Engineering properties such as onset temperature, peak temperature, end temperature, gelatinization enthalpy, specific heat capacity, co-efficient of static friction and angle of repose were determined using standard procedures.

Co-efficient of friction: The coefficient of friction for the starch was determined using the method documented by Bahnasawy (2007). The coefficient of friction was tested

against plywood, stainless steel, galvanized steel and glass. A bottomless cylinder of 5 cm diameter and 10 cm height was filled with the starch sample and placed over the different surfaces which in turn were placed on an inclined plane system. The surfaces were gently raised using a jack and the angle at which the powder motion began as the inclined plane was read off a calibrated protractor in degrees. The coefficient of friction was calculated as using equation 9:

$$\mu = \tan \alpha \tag{9}$$

Where: μ = coefficient of friction; α = angle, in degrees.

Angle of repose: The emptying method documented by Garnayak *et al.* (2008) was adopted. A bottomless cylinder of 5 cm diameter and 10 cm height was placed over a plane surface and the starch samples placed in the cylinder. The cylinder was raised slowly allowing the sample to flow down and form a natural slope. The angle of repose was calculated from the height and diameter of the pile using equation 10:

$$\theta = \tan^{-1} \frac{2h}{D} \tag{10}$$

Where: θ = angle of repose, °, h = height, cm, D = diameter, cm.

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC): A PerkinElmer Diamond-I DSC with an internal coolant (Intercooler 1P) and nitrogen purge gas were used in the experimental study. The melting point and enthalpies of indium were used for temperature and heat capacity calibration, respectively. A high-pressure stainless-steel pan (PE nr B0182901) with a gold-plated copper seal (PE nr 042-191758) was used to achieve constant moisture content at high temperature during DSC measurements. The sample mass used for the study was about 35 mg. A heating rate of 5 °C/min was used to minimize any temperature lag due to the large mass of the steel pan. The onset temperature (T_o), peak temperature (T_p), conclusion temperature (T_c), and enthalpy (H) of starch gelatinization were obtained from DSC thermograms, with enthalpy being calculated based on the weight of dry starch.

Visco-elastic properties of *acha* starch flour: The viscosity values of *acha* starch flour were determined using a HAAKE Viscotester 500 (Thermo Fisher Scientific Pty Ltd. D-76227 Karlsruhe, Germany). The *acha* starch suspension (2 – 20 w/v) prepared inside a test-tube was heated using a shaking bath to a preset temperature (60 – 90 °C). The experimental runs were planned using Design Expert software.

Statistical Analysis

A comprehensive analysis of the data was conducted using Design Expert 13 (Windows software) to summarize the findings using descriptive analysis and draw conclusions about relationships between variables utilising inferential analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The native and modified *acha* starch yield was presented in Table 1. The native and modified starch yield values were 77.14 and 75.10%, respectively. The native starch value obtained was higher than 50.60 and 75.5% documented by Olu-Owolabi (2014) and Arueya and Oyewale (2015) for native *acha* starch. The difference in the yield of native *acha* starch may be associated with differences in extraction or purification processes. The native starch yield value obtained was higher than 11.53, 24, 20 – 35 and 45.3 % reported for potato, sorghum, cassava and *Musa* spp. (ABB), respectively (Adebayo *et al.*, 2021; Chisenga, 2021; Ali *et al.*, 2023). The higher values in starch yield from *acha* may be attributed to the starch content present in the grains which indicates that *acha* starch can serve as a potential alternative starch source. But the modified starch yield obtained was lower than 95.3 and 93.71% reported for modified *Musa* spp. (ABB) and sweet potato starch, respectively (Adebayo *et al.*, 2021; Nithiyananthan, 2022).

The initial moisture content values for native and modified *acha* starch were presented in Table 1. The initial moisture content values for native and modified *acha* starch are 10.6 and 9.49%, respectively. The initial moisture content for native starch obtained was higher than 2.85 and 8.76% reported for potato and yam starches, respectively but lower than 13.20 and 15.05% reported for white yam and cocoyam starches (Arawande and Ashogbon, 2019; Oliveira *et al.*, 2021; Okereke *et al.*, 2022). While, modified *acha* starch value obtained compared favorably with 11.40% for modified white cocoyam but higher than 1.35% for modified *Musa* spp. (ABB) (Adebayo *et al.*, 2020; Okereke *et al.*, 2022). The moisture content of starch plays an important role in determining its keeping quality and storage stability. The lower the moisture content, the higher the stability (Adebayo *et al.*, 2021). Starch with moisture content lower than 14% can resist microbial growth and hence are storage stable (Adebayo *et al.*, 2021). This indicates that both native and modified *acha* starches are shelf stable and will not undergo moisture-related deterioration.

The bulk density values for native and modified *acha* starch were presented in Table 1. The bulk density values of native and modified *acha* starch were 0.32 and 0.36 g/ml (loose) and 0.39 and 0.48 g/ml (packed), respectively. The bulk density values obtained were lower than 0.51 g/ml (loose) and 0.66 g/ml (packed) for potato starch (Table 1). The bulk density (loose or packed) values for native *acha* starch were lower than 0.88, 0.65 and 0.68 g/ml for cocoyam, *Musa* spp. (ABB) and breadfruit starch, respectively (Arawande and Ashogbon, 2019; Adebayo *et al.*, 2021). The modified packed bulk density values were lower than 0.62 and 0.54 g/ml documented for modified white and red cocoyam starch (Okunade and Arinola, 2021). The results showed that starch modification improved both loose and packed density. Bulk density is an essential parameter for process development. It is used in determining the amount of powder that can fit in a space and indicates compactness (Amidon *et al.*, 2017).

The density ratio and porosity values for native and modified *acha* starch were presented in Table 1. The values for density ratio of modified and native starch were 75.20 and 82.20%, respectively. The native starch density ratio value compared favorably with 82.46% reported for white cocoyam starch but higher than 77% documented for *Musa* spp. (ABB) starch (Adebayo *et al.*, 2021; Okunade and Arinola, 2021) while, the modified starch density ratio value obtained compared favorably with 74.00 and 76.53% for modified *Musa* spp. (ABB) and potato starch, respectively but lower than 80.64% reported for white cocoyam starch (Adebayo *et al.*, 2021; Okunade and Arinola, 2021).

The values for porosity of native and modified starch were 17.80 and 24.78%, respectively (Table 1). The *acha* native starch porosity value obtained compared favorably with 17.54% reported for white cocoyam starch. Also, the porosity value was higher than 15.79% documented for red cocoyam starch but lower than 23.47% for potato starch (Okunade and Arinola, 2021) while, *acha* modified starch porosity value compared favorably with 25.74% for *Musa* spp. (ABB) but higher than 14.81 and 19.35% for modified red and white cocoyam, respectively (Adebayo *et al.*, 2021;

Table 1: Physiochemical Characteristics of *Acha* Starch

Parameters	Native starch	Modified starch	Potato starch
Starch yield (%)	77.14	75.10	11.53
Moisture content (%) d.b	10.64±0.12 ^c	9.49±0.14 ^b	2.85±0.02 ^a
Loose bulk density (g/ml)	0.32±0.00 ^a	0.36±0.00 ^b	0.51±0.02 ^c
Packed bulk density (g/ml)	0.39±0.00 ^a	0.48±0.00 ^b	0.66±0.03 ^c
Carr index (%)	21.28±2.02 ^a	33.00±3.27 ^c	30.61±0.02 ^b
Hausner ratio	1.22±0.27 ^a	1.33±0.03 ^c	1.31±0.02 ^b
Density ratio (%)	82.19±1.82 ^b	75.22±1.86 ^a	76.53±0.03 ^a
Porosity (%)	17.80±1.83 ^a	24.78±1.86 ^b	23.47±0.02 ^b
Angle of repose (°)	44.70±1.15 ^b	51.43±0.51 ^c	39.78±0.10 ^a
Moisture content (%)	10.64±0.12 ^c	9.49±0.14 ^b	2.85±0.02 ^a
Compressibility	Fair	Good	Good
Flowability	Fair	Poor	Good

Values reported are mean ± standard deviation in triplicate; Mean values within each row bearing a different superscript roman letter are significantly different ($p \leq 0.05$)

Okunade and Arinola, 2021). Porosity measures the percentage of voids of an unconsolidated mass of materials often needed in air and heat flow studies as well as other application (Adebayo *et al.*, 2021).

al., 2021). Though, contrary trends are documented for native and modified red cocoyam starch (8 and 10%) and native and succinylated breadfruit starch (14 and 16 %) (Awokoya *et al.*, 2018; Okunade and Arinola, 2021). Using

Table 2: Flowability Classification (Carr standard) (Carr, 1965)

Carr's index	Flowability	Hausner ratio
≤ 10	Excellent	1.00 – 1.11
11.0 – 15.0	Good	1.12 – 1.18
16 – 20	Fair	1.19 – 1.25
21 -25	Passable	1.26 – 1.34
26 -31	Poor	1.35 – 1.45
32 – 37	Very poor	1.46- 1.59
> 38	Awful	> 1.60

Table 3: Gelation and Least Gelation of *Acha* sStarch and Potato Starch

Concentration (%)	Native Starch	Modified Starch	Potato Starch
2	--	--	--
4	--	--	--
6	- +	--	--
8	- +	++	--
10	++	++	--
12	++	++	--
14	++	++	--
16	++	++	++
18	++	++	++
20	++	++	++
LGC	10%	8%	16%

-- no gelation; -+ viscous; ++ full gelation; LGC – Least Gelation Concentration

The Carr index and Hausner ratio values of native and modified *acha* starch were presented in Table 1. Carr index and Hausner ratio of native and modified starch were 21.28% and 1.22; 33% and 1.33, respectively. The Carr index and Hausner ratio values for native starch compared favorably with 21.28% and 1.21; 21.95% and 1.28 for white cocoyam and yam starch, respectively (Oluwasina *et al.*, 2017; Okunade and Arinola, 2021). Also, the Carr index and Hausner ratio values for modified *acha* starch compared favorably with 30.61% and 1.31 for potato starch but higher than 24% and 1.24 reported for modified white yam starch (Okunade and Arinola, 2021). The native starch showed a fair compactness but passable flowability while modified starch showed higher compactness but very poor flowability based on Carr index (Table 2). The native starch showed fair flowability, while modified starch shows a passable flowability based on Hausner ratio (Table 2). This showed that starch modification did not improve flowability but influences compressibility (Adebayo *et al.*, 2021; Okunade and Arinola, 2021).

The gelation and least gelation concentration of the native and modified *acha* starch were presented in Table 3. The table showed that full gelation occurred at 8 and 10% for modified and native *acha* starch, respectively though Arueya and Oyewale (2015) reported that native and modified *acha* starch occurred at 6 and 8%, respectively. The values obtained showed similar trends with modified and native cassava starch (6.8 and 8%) and modified and native *Musa* spp. (ABB) (8 and 14%) (Adebayo *et al.*, 2021; Okereke *et*

least gelation concentration as gelation capacity index, the lower the least gelation concentration, the higher the gelation properties of starch. Therefore, modified starch exhibited a higher gelation property. Therefore, *acha* starch could be implored as a good gelling agent in food development and formulation.

The amylose, amylopectin and amylose-amylopectin ratio were presented in Table 4. The amylose content values for native and modified starch were 24.07 and 24.60%, respectively. The amylose value for native starch compared favorably with 23.50% reported for cocoyam but lower than 25.77 and 29.77% reported for yam and potato starch (Arawande and Ashogbon, 2019; Oliveira *et al.*, 2021).

The amylopectin content values for modified and native *acha* starch were 75.40 and 75.93%, respectively. The amylopectin content of native starch compared favorably with 75.77 and 76.50% reported for cocoyam and yam starch, respectively. The value obtained was higher than 70.23% documented for potato starch but lower than 78.40% reported for cassava starch (Arawande and Oliveira *et al.*, 2021; Oluwasina *et al.*, 2021).

The amylose-amylopectin ratio values for native and modified *acha* starch were 0.32 and 0.33, respectively. The amylose-amylopectin ratio values for native and modified *acha* starch values were lower than 0.42 for potato starch (Table 4).

Amylose-amylopectin ratio is an indicator of glycemic index - the lower the amylose-amylopectin ratio, the lower the glycemic index (Murugadass *et al.*, 2018). The low glycemic index of *acha* starch could be explored in food formulations intended for diabetic consumers.

native and modified *acha* starch were 82.6, 92.3, 96.7 and 14.1 °C; and 83.6, 87.38, 89.62 and 6.3 °C, respectively. The onset temperature, peak temperature, end temperature and temperature range values obtained for native and modified starch were lower than 72.7, 106.4, 106.2 and 33.5 °C for potato starch but higher than 81.3, 85.2, 93.0 and

Table 4: Amylose and Amylopectin Composition of *Acha* Starch

Parameter	Samples		
	Native starch	Modified starch	Potato starch
Amylose (%)	24.07±0.06a	24.60±0.03b	29.77±0.02c
Amylopectin (%)	75.93±0.06c	75.40±0.03b	70.23±0.02a
Amylose/amylopectin	0.32±0.00	0.33±0.00	0.42±0.00

Values reported are mean ± standard deviation in triplicate; Mean values within each row bearing a different superscript roman letter are significantly ($p < 5\%$) different.

Table 5: Coefficient of Static Friction for *Acha* Starch

Sample	Glass	Wood	G. steel	S. steel
Native	0.68±0.06a	0.71±0.48a	0.71±0.04a	0.63±0.07a
Modified	0.68±0.02a	0.77±0.08a	0.73±0.09b	0.70±0.05ab
P. starch	0.51±0.02a	0.66±0.03a	0.61±0.02a	0.57±0.03b

G. steel – Galvanized steel, S. steel – Stainless steel; P. starch – Potato starch

Mean values within each row bearing a different superscript roman letter are significant ($p \leq 0.05$) difference

Table 6: Thermal Characterization of *Acha* Starch using Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC)

Parameters	Native Starch	Modified Starch	Potato Starch
Onset Temperature, TO	82.6°C	83.6 °C	72.7 °C
Peak Temperature, TP	92.3 °C	87.38°C	106.4 °C
End Temperature, TE	96.7 °C	89.6 °C	106.2 °C
Temperature Range	14.13 °C	6.27 °C	33.5 °C

The coefficient of static friction values is presented in Table 5. The coefficient of static friction values for native and modified *acha* starch were 0.68 and 0.68; 0.71 and 0.77; 0.71 and 0.73; 0.63 and 0.70, on glass, plywood, galvanized steel and stainless steel, respectively. The coefficient of static friction (galvanized steel and plywood) values for native and modified starch compared favorably with 0.61 and 0.66 for potato starch. The coefficient of friction helps in designing efficient handling systems to prevent flow issues.

The values for angle of repose were presented in Table 1. The angle of repose values for native and modified starch is 44.70 and 51.48°, respectively.

The angle of repose is an indication of the flow rate of the starch powder extracted. According to Carr (1976) classification, angles of up to 35° indicated free flowability, 35 – 45° some cohesiveness, 45 – 55° cohesiveness (loss of free flowability), and 55° and above very high cohesiveness and, therefore, very limited (or no) flowability. Therefore, the native starch and modified starch exhibited cohesiveness in the flow rate.

Thermal properties of native and acidified *acha* starch were presented in Table 6. The onset temperature, peak temperature, end temperature and temperature range for

11.7 °C for potato and cocoyam starch, respectively (Aranwande and Ashongbon, 2019). The gelatinization temperature depends on the microstructure and degree of crystallization with the granules and also the granules size and amylose-amylopectin ratio (Aranwande and Ashongbon, 2019).

The pasting properties of both native and modified *acha* starch are presented in Table 7. The peak viscosity, trough, breakdown, final viscosity, setback, peak time and pasting temperature for both native and modified starch were 502.25 and 504.25 RVU; 245.42 and 269.42 RVU; 342.44 and 356.03 RVU; 396.29 and 397.42 RVU, 56.41 and 56.95 RVU; 5.26 and 5.37 min. and 70.33 and 70.50 °C, respectively. The peak viscosity values for both native and modified *acha* starch were lower than 790 RVU recorded by Jideani and Akingbala (1993). The peak viscosity values obtained for both native and modified *acha* starch were higher than 204.5, 265.1, 211.3, 104, 121.25 and 175.7 RVU reported for elephant yam, sweet potato, rice, wheat, breadfruit and corn starch, respectively but lower than 791 RVU reported for potato starch (Jane *et al.*, 1999; Srichuwong *et al.*, 2005; Akanbi *et al.*, 2009). The peak viscosity values for both native and modified *acha* starch suggested that they possess a strong ability to thicken and gelatinize (Liang and King, 2003). The trough viscosity

values obtained for both native and modified *acha* starch compared favorably with 228.3 recorded for potato starch but higher than 111.8, 114.0, 86.2, 75, 113.33 and 90.5 RVU reported for elephant yam, sweet potato, rice, wheat, breadfruit and corn starch, respectively (Jane *et al.*, 1999; Srichuwong *et al.*, 2005; Akanbi *et al.*, 2009). The high trough viscosity values suggest that both native and modified *acha* starch is stable during heating and mechanical processing (Bakare, 2008). Also, breakdown viscosity values obtained for both native and modified *acha* starch were higher than 92.5, 151.1, 125.1, 72, 7.92 and 85.2 RVU reported for elephant yam, sweet potato, rice, wheat, breadfruit and corn starch, respectively but lower than 563.1 RVU reported for potato starch (Jane *et al.*, 1999; Srichuwong *et al.*, 2005; Akanbi *et al.*, 2009). The high breakdown viscosity values are indicative of paste stability (Akanbi *et al.*, 2009).

The final viscosity of native and modified *acha* starch was higher than 197.5, 269.8, 286.8, 170.7, 154, 153.42 and

processing, thereby preserving its functional qualities for a wide range of applications, from baked goods to dairy products. It also indicates high water-binding capacity, higher gelatinization tendency and lower swelling property starch-based flour due to the degree of associative forces between the starch granules (Adebowale *et al.*, 2005).

The effects of temperature and concentration on viscosity of native and modified starch are presented in Figure 1.

The viscosity ranged from 408.65 – 665.2 mPas and 417.9 – 447.1 mPas for native and modified starch, respectively. Figure 1 (A) showed that as starch concentration increased, there is a corresponding increase in viscosity in both native and modified *acha* starch. Also, as temperature increased from 60 – 90 °C, there was a corresponding increase in viscosity of the starch. Although, the interactive effect of concentration and temperature on viscosity is linear for native starch while that of modified starch is non-linear (Figure 1 (B)).

Table 7: Pasting Properties of *Acha* Starch

Parameter	Starch Samples		
	Native	Modified	Potato
Peak Viscosity (RVU)	502.25	504.25	791.4
Trough (RVU)	245.42	269.42	228.3
Breakdown (RVU)	342.44	356.03	563.1
Final Viscosity (RVU)	396.29	397.42	286.8
Setback (RVU)	56.41	56.95	58.5
Peak time (min.)	5.26	5.37	5.1
Pasting temp. (°C)	70.33	70.50	67.3

167.5 RVU reported for elephant yam, sweet potato, potato, rice, wheat, breadfruit and corn starch, respectively (Jane *et al.*, 1999; Srichuwong *et al.*, 2005; Akanbi *et al.*, 2009). The higher final viscosity values suggest that *acha* starch retrograde faster (Lii *et al.*, 1996). The setback viscosity values obtained for both native and modified *acha* starch were lower than 85.7, 73.3, 84.5, 79, and 77 RVU recorded for elephant yam, sweet potato, rice, wheat and corn, respectively. Although, it compared favorably with 58.4 RVU recorded for potato and higher than 40.08 RVU recorded for breadfruit (Jane *et al.*, 1999; Srichuwong *et al.*, 2005; Akanbi *et al.*, 2009). The setback viscosity of *acha* starch indicated that it is less susceptible to retrogradation during cooling (Aidoo *et al.*, 2022). The peak time values for both native and modified *acha* starch were lower than 7.5, 7.0, 8.5, and 8.5 min. reported for elephant yam, sweet potato, rice and corn, respectively and compared favorably with 5.1 min. reported for potato (Srichuwong *et al.*, 2005). This moderate peak time allows for more controlled gelatinization, giving manufacturers more flexibility in managing texture during production. The pasting temperature for both native and modified *acha* starch compared favorably with 71.3 °C reported for rice. The values were lower than 81.6, 75.2, 88.6, 84.05 and 82.0 °C reported for elephant yam, sweet potato, wheat, breadfruit and corn starch, respectively but higher than 67.3 °C reported for potato and (Jane *et al.*, 1999; Srichuwong *et al.*, 2005; Akanbi *et al.*, 2009). The pasting temperature of *acha* starch indicates effective gelatinization without over-

CONCLUSION

This study investigated the physicochemical and engineering properties and proximate composition of *acha* starch with the view of providing engineering data that would extend its usage in the food processing industry. Therefore, the following conclusions may be drawn from the study:

- i. *Acha* starch flour exhibited favourable engineering properties and glycaemic index. Therefore, it may find application in food formulation and development.
- ii. Modified *acha* starch had good compressibility and poor flowability while native *acha* starch had poor compressibility and fair flowability.
- iii. Viscosity of both native and modified *acha* starch flour depends on concentration and temperature.

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